

Fufu Production and Marketing in Ijebu-North Local Government Area 1982-2024

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Abstract:

This study examined the historical evolution, production processes, marketing systems, and socio-economic impacts of *fufu* production in Ijebu-North Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. The work situates *fufu* within the broader context of cassava cultivation, indigenous food processing, and rural livelihoods. Cassava, a major staple crop in Nigeria, is central to food security, household income, and cultural identity in Ijebu communities. The study revealed that *fufu* production evolved from a domestic, subsistence practice into a vibrant small-scale commercial enterprise, largely driven by women and family labour. It established that its production remains predominantly manual, relying on indigenous knowledge systems, with limited mechanisation due to high costs, poor electricity supply, and inadequate institutional support. Marketing has expanded from local periodic markets to inter-regional trade linking rural producers with urban centres such as Abeokuta, Ibadan, and Lagos. Despite the challenges of transportation, storage, and dependence on middlemen, *fufu* production provides a steady income, supports education and household welfare, generates rural employment, and contributes to local government revenue through market levies. Primary sources, such as oral interviews from producers and marketers, and secondary sources, like books, journal articles, and internet materials, were used. *Fufu* production, therefore, represents a gendered, culturally embedded rural economy that plays an important role in local food systems.

Keywords: Fufu, Production and Marketing, Ijebu-North, Local Government.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, millions of people are being supported by root crops. These staple food crops are cultivated by a significant number of farmers in the tropics for direct human consumption and industrial purposes (Oladele *et al*, 2020, 5-18). In Nigeria, staple food items are produced all-year-round in all the ecological zones, depending on the availability of moisture. Cassava, yams, corn, coco-yams, cowpeas, beans, sweet potatoes, millet, plantains, bananas, rice, sorghum, and a variety of fruits and vegetables are the most significant staple food crops grown by farmers in Nigeria, with cassava being amongst the most abundant and consumed (Olanrewaju 2020).

Cassava belongs to the family of *Euphorbiaceae*, and it is the seventh most important crop in the world, thus constituting a staple food for about 800 million people (Hahn and Keyer 1985). Cassava roots contain mainly carbohydrates, of which 80% is starch and less than 1% fat. By this, cassava plays an important role in alleviating the African Food Crisis, though low in protein (1.20%) and rich in cyanide (> 10 mg/100 g fresh weight), varieties are classified as TMS 50395 (Reference Manual, IITA, Ibadan, Nigeria, 1990). The Portuguese explorers introduced it into central Africa from South America in the 16th century, and probably the emancipated slaves introduced the crop to Nigeria, as they returned to the country from South America via the Islands of Sao Tome and Fernando Po (Nnedinso 2020).

Nigeria is a leading producer of cassava in large quantities in the world, with an annual production of about 45 million tons (Asante-Pok 2013). Cassava is a reliable source of calories for Nigerians, and over 80% of those living in rural areas consume its products daily (Okpara *et al*, 2023). In addition to improving the nation's food security, it has boosted Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and created jobs in specialised industries like farming, processing, and marketing. Almost every household in the southern part of Nigeria grows cassava, making it one of the most widely grown and marketed agricultural commodities in the region. Cassava is processed and marketed in the form of *garri*, *fufu*, *lafu*, processed dried chips and pellets, starch, bread, biscuits, paperboard, beer, sugar syrup, ethanol, high-quality cassava flour (HQCF), and glue for industrial use (Iwuoha and Eke 1996).

Fufu, one of the products of cassava, is a meal of soaked fermented cassava roots which is widely consumed in Nigeria (Hahn 1988). It is one of the major food forms of cassava fermentation, which is reconstituted by stirring in boiling water to form dough and eaten with flavoured sauces. In some areas, low cyanide cassava roots can be boiled or steamed and pounded into *fufu* (Bamidele *et al*, 2015). *Fufu* contains 6.50, 1.68, 1.32, 1.84, 1.42 and 87.24% moisture, protein, fat, ash, crude fibre and carbohydrate, respectively (Owolarafe *et al*, 2018). The cassava tubers are peeled, washed, cut into thick chunks, and steeped in water in earthenware pots or in a slow-flowing stream between 4 and 5 days to ferment, soften and produce a characteristic of retted cassava meal. The tubers are disintegrated in clean water, sieved and allowed to settle for decantation of water; the sediment is the *fufu* (raw) (Okafor *et al*, 1984). There are two modified methods used in *fufu* production: peeling the cassava tubers, cutting them into smaller cubes of

about 2-4 cm before soaking, or grating the tubers into a mash, bagging the mash and pressing out some liquid before soaking the bag in water. The second method is using the odourless flour technique on yellow cassava roots. One potential problem in processed *fufu* is the flavour of the product, which may be undesirable to many people (Okafor *et al*, 1984). Another major problem with *fufu* production is that the quality of the product varies from one processor to another and from one processing batch to another by the same processor. Factors that could be responsible for the variability of the quality of *fufu* include the following: the size to which the roots are cut before soaking, variety differences in dry matter content and the quality of roots or water used for soaking (Nwajiuba 1995).

Various socio-economic, cultural, and technological factors led to the emergence of *fufu* production and marketing in Ijebu North Local Government Area of Ogun State between 1982 and 2024. The people's preference for *fufu* as a staple carbohydrate source has contributed to its steady production over the years. Therefore, this study examined *fufu* production, marketing, and impact in Ijebu North Local Government Area. Over time, mechanisation and improved processing techniques have led to larger-scale production and commercialisation. Despite the economic benefits of *fufu* production, many local processors and marketers are faced with inadequate processing facilities, limited access to credit, and fluctuating market demand. Understanding these challenges is essential to improve production efficiency and market strategies in Ijebu North Local Government Area.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This paper reviews relevant materials on cassava and *fufu* production, marketing and impacts in Ijebu North Local Government Area. Adebayo's work on *Ago-Iwoye, History, Culture and Traditional Administration*, traces the origins of Ago-Iwoye to over 600 years ago, connecting the town to the Yoruba progenitor, Oduduwa, and the Osemawe of Ondo. It also explores the town's history, festivals, such as *Seere, Igbe, Eibi, Oro, Ogun, Agemo*, and various social organisations (Adebayo 2000). The book provides a valuable historical and cultural context of Ago-Iwoye's involvement in *fufu* production. Ayandele described the Ijebu people as industrious with rich cultural traditions. He examined the political, economic, and cultural structures of the Ijebu kingdom, including their role in the Yoruba civil war, and concluded by detailing the British annexation of Ijebu in 1892 during the Imagbon War (Ayandele 1992). Usman and Falola in *The Yoruba from Prehistory to the Present* meticulously presents the history of the Yoruba people, including the Ijebu, through archaeological and anthropological evidence. The work highlights the Ijebu's advanced trade systems and economic contributions to their regional influence, as well as exploring how their cultural and spiritual connections with Ilé-Ifè shaped their identity (Usman and Falola 2019).

Owolarafe *et al.*, examined *fufu* processing techniques in Ilaro and Abeokuta, noting significant differences based on adopted methods. Most centres were individually

owned and relied on manual labour, leading to low income and high drudgery. They argued that most of the challenges faced by the people are inadequate funding, limited education, and slow adoption of modern technologies (Owolarafe et al, 2018). Ali, Odusina, and Olawumi's *Determinants of Output of Cassava Products in Ogun State, Nigeria*, acknowledges Nigeria as the world's leading cassava producer, highlighting its economic and nutritional significance. It emphasised that processing cassava into products like *fufu* is profitable, but rising costs of roots and labour hindered output. The study revealed that improving production efficiency and road infrastructure would reduce cassava costs and boost profitability (Ali et al, 2023, 9-14).

This work examined the important role women play in cassava processing in Ijebu Ode. It revealed that most of those who engaged in the commercial activity were middle-aged, married women. Major constraints in the business included lack of credit, high costs, poor market access, and limited support services. Credit access from government and NGOs to boost women's productivity in cassava processing are recommended (Ibitunde et al, 2021). The analysis of cassava products marketing in Abia State, Nigeria revealed that cassava product marketers are young, educated, and moderately experienced, with *gari* being the most profitable product. In order to improve profits through shared resources and economies of scale, forming of cooperatives to reduce marketing costs was recommended (Okpara et al, 2023).

Dipeolu, et al. (2001), *Fufu Marketing Systems in South-West Nigeria*, unveiled that favourable location and market access significantly influence the commercial marketing of *fufu*, thus putting those in remote area at disadvantaged. They noted that despite *fufu*'s popularity in urban southwest Nigeria, there is little evidence of significant market expansion (Dipeolu et al, 2001). A study revealed that in Udi LGA in Enugu State, *fufu* is the highest profit margins among cassava products, while *garri* remained the most popular staple. It also identified that the key challenges experienced by the people are poor roads, high costs, and lack of storage, prompting calls for government support and farmers cooperatives (Nnedinso and Ugwoke 2020).

Ajala and Lasisi's *Effects of Transportation Challenges on Fufu Production in Yewa South Local Government Area Ogun State Nigeria* found that transportation significantly influenced *fufu* processors' productivity, accounting for 36% of production variation. It was concluded that improving transport services would enhance overall food processing and supply efficiency (Ajala and Lasisi 2019). A study on production of *fufu* from yellow cassava roots using the odourless flour technique and the traditional method to evaluate carotenoids retention in *fufu* revealed that water and heat during processing did not reduce carotene content, but sun-drying method negatively affected pro-Vitamin A levels in *fufu*. The study recommended traditional methods for yellow cassava processing and technology transfer to rural communities to combat Vitamin A Deficiency (VAD) (Omodamiro et al, 2012). A study on CMD-resistant cassava varieties in Umudike revealed that *fufu* flours, with low moisture, high carbohydrate, and good shelf life, are ideal for rural consumers. It also highlighted desirable processing traits such as water absorption, bulk density, and pasting properties for efficient handling, packaging, and

dough preparation (Etudaiye, 2020). Another study showed that Nigeria's cassava production was estimated at 34–37 million tonnes in the early 2000s, with some variation across FAO and CBN data. Cassava ranked as the highest-produced crop in Nigeria, ahead of yam, sorghum, millet, and rice (Truman *et al*, 2004).

Findings from a study suggest that transportation bridges the gap between production and delivery, but agrarian communities in Ijebu North face challenges such as poor roads and high transport costs. These issues negatively affect both production efficiency and product pricing (Afolabi *et al*, 2016). The work on comparative assessment of gari and *fufu* marketing in Umuahia North Local Government Area, Abia State, observed that while cassava product marketing in Abia State can drive economic growth, most markets remain underdeveloped with poor infrastructure, unstable prices, and high transport costs. Long travel distances for trade often disrupt supply-demand balance and inflate prices (Uzuegbu *et al*, 2020). *Fufu* production and marketing in Ijebu North (1982–2024) play a crucial role in the local economy and food security in Nigeria at large. Various studies have investigated the production of *fufu* from cassava and the marketing process by stressing its economic value and marketing challenges caused by poor infrastructure, high cost of transportation, inadequate funding, and low adoption of technology. This study aims to address gaps in processing methods and market access, promoting sustainable growth for small-scale producers.

3. METHODS AND DISCUSSION

Data collected for this research included both primary and secondary sources of historical writing. Primary data gathered through in-depth oral interviews to elicit the discourse on *fufu* production and marketing in Ijebu-North local government and how this business has been a means of livelihood for many people and created employment for individuals in the area. *Fufu* production represents a gendered, culturally embedded rural economy that plays an important role in local food systems. Secondary sources of data were derived from relevant books, journal articles, and internet materials, focusing on relevance and importance of *fufu* business in the region and its economic advantage. The subtopic discusses the focus of this research.

3.1 *Fufu* production and marketing in Ijebu north local government

Fufu production in Ijebu North Local Government evolved from a strictly domestic culinary practice to a vibrant commercial enterprise that sustains numerous households economically and socially. Historically, cassava production was introduced to West Africa by Portuguese traders in the 16th century. The region's abundant cassava production, fertile land, and communal food practices made *fufu* not only a staple diet but also a means of livelihood for many women, youths, and family-run enterprises (Ikuemonisan *et al*, 2020). The tradition of cassava processing in Ijebuland, which includes Ago-Iwoye, Awa-Ijebu, Oru, and Ijebu-Igbo, gained prominence as a food crop due to the colonial-era agricultural reforms that encouraged the cultivation of root crops (Ikuemonisan *et al*,

2020). Women, in particular, were involved in the processing of cassava into *fufu* as a daily survival skill, although *fufu* production had already become an essential part of local diets which generated income for rural households. Because of its prominence in rural areas, the rural populations had to depend more on local resources for production.

Cassava, which is a tuber crop used for *fufu* production, is cultivated either as a subsistence or as a mechanised form. The production of *fufu* expanded from household kitchens to public markets from one generation to another (Ibitunde *et al*, 2021). In Ago-Iwoye, for instance, aged female processors remember how they transitioned from processing for domestic use to producing for sale to support their families during economic downturns. Mrs. Aderonke affirmed that she learned about *fufu* processing and production from her mother at a young age while growing up and has served as a source of livelihood for her and her family.ⁱ However, the growing population and the high demand by people made *fufu* producers begin to settle into regular supply chains with traders, hoteliers, and bulk buyers. Mrs Fadipe, explained that apart from selling to people or family who intended to eat, she also sold to food sellers, party event planners, and hotel owners through phone orders or visits from buyers seeking fresh *fufu*.ⁱⁱ A vital aspect of *fufu* production is the sourcing of cassava tubers. Many *fufu* processors in Ijebu North Local Government area rely on a dual strategy of subsistence and commercial acquisition. An interviewee, Mrs Fadipe, stated that she cultivates her own cassava and supplements her stock from local village markets.ⁱⁱⁱ This dual model of cassava sourcing is common, especially in households with access to farmland. The practice led to the intersection between agriculture and food processing and production at the grassroots, reinforcing the essential role of family economy in rural food chains.

Fufu production involves several traditional steps: peeling, soaking, fermenting, mashing, sieving, dewatering, and either cooking or drying. These largely manual steps are passed down through generations, although some modern tools, like local graters or mechanical presses, are now in use. An interviewee, Mrs. Aderonke, elucidated that after peeling the cassava, it is soaked for 3 to 4 days to ferment before mashing and pressing.^{iv} This technique, as corroborated by other processors from Ago-Iwoye, Awa, Ijebu-Igbo, and Oru, ensures that the final product retains the unique texture and aroma cherished by consumers. The fermentation process also acts as a preservation method, which makes the cassava more digestible. Notably, methods differ slightly based on community practices.

In Ago-Iwoye, processors may soak cassava for up to 5 days, while in Ijebu-Igbo, 3-day fermentation is common, especially when the weather is warm. Such flexibility indicates an indigenous knowledge system responsive to environmental and seasonal conditions. *Fufu* processing is time-intensive, as explained by Mrs Titi, who revealed that *fufu* processing from start to finish takes a long time, as a batch can take 5 to 7 days, depending on weather and soaking time,^v as weather conditions greatly influence fermentation speed and drying effectiveness. During rainy seasons, drying becomes difficult, thereby extending the timeline or resulting in spoilage. Despite the long production time, output is always considerable.

On average, processors produced 30 to 50 portions per batch, depending on the amount of processed cassava and family support.^{vi} These outputs are typically scaled to market demands and household capacity. Markets in Ijebu North operate on fixed days, which are well-integrated into the rural economy and *Fufu* is sold both in fresh and dried forms. Fresh *fufu* is typically packaged in nylon bags or plastic bowls and sold to walk-in customers or local food vendors. Pricing fluctuates based on cassava availability, transportation costs, and demand. A single bowl of fresh *fufu* could be sold between ₦300 – ₦500, while dried *fufu*, considered more shelf-stable and in demand among city traders, is priced higher, while dried *fufu* is sometimes exported to urban centres like Abeokuta and Ibadan through middlemen or relatives in those cities. Transportation of the *fufu* from production sites to markets is a critical concern as many producers use motorcycles (*Okada*) or tricycles (*Keke*), to carry larger batches through hired pickups (Ajala and Lasisi 2019). However, the poor road infrastructure in some Ijebu North communities, such as parts of Awa, Ago-Iwoye, and Ijebu-Igbo complicates the process. An interviewee, Mr. Seyi, explained that roads in some distant villages within the town where the *fufu* is produced have bad road networks to the extent that during the rainy season this sometimes affects delivery to market women and ceremonies.^{vii}

Fufu production is both a livelihood and a means of social empowerment among many women processors. It is emphasized that proceeds from sales have become sources of financial support to families in paying children's school fees and participating in local cooperative groups such as the Cassava Processors Cooperative (CPC). The women's participation in the local cooperative groups enabled them to pool resources and receive financial support in the form of soft loans to expand their businesses. Mrs Abosede stated that she is a member of a cooperative society whose members are mostly in the same line of business, *fufu* production. The business organization allows each member to give a flexible donation, which gives members the opportunity to receive loans.^{viii} In other words, many of the women interviewed have received significant economic benefits from *fufu* production in sustaining their households, despite their limited formal education.

3.2 Processing, packaging and marketing of fufu

The processing and marketing of *fufu* in Ijebu North Local Government has historically evolved from subsistence-level barter exchanges to organised local commerce, deeply rooted in communal and family networks. In the early 1990s, producers often relied solely on local weekly markets such as Obada and Atikori markets in Ijebu-Igbo, and Oke-Aje in Ijebu-Ode for *fufu* transactions. At that time, transactions were largely informal, and marketing involved physical presence, verbal negotiation, and cash payments with minimal packaging or preservation.^{ix} However, the economic liberalisation of the late 1990s and early 2000s led to a significant increase in rural-urban linkages, opening new opportunities for distribution. Many women who are *fufu* sellers in Ago-Iwoye, Oru and Ijebu-Igbo claimed that they have been producing *fufu* for over a decade. They sold *fufu* both fresh and dried, packaged in nylon bags or bowls, depending on customer preference.

Some of the customers are urban traders from Ibadan and Abeokuta who usually come into the community to purchase *fufu* in bulk for resale.^x This form of decentralised but structured market interaction is now a dominant feature of the *fufu* business in the area. Distribution strategies have also changed. While small-scale producers still use *Okada* (motorcycles) or *Keke napep* (tricycles) to transport goods to the market, those handling larger volumes now engage pickup vans, thus extending *fufu* distribution beyond Ijebu communities to cities in Ogun and Oyo States.^{xi} In terms of pricing, producers often experience volatility. Cassava, the primary raw material, fluctuates in price due to seasonal changes, supply shortages, and middleman influence. Whenever a *fufu* producer of a small-scale production is unable to harvest from his or her own farm, the producer can spend about ₦10,000 weekly on cassava purchases, and when the business is favourable, the producer can earn up to ₦15,000 weekly. But profit margins are often affected by low purchase prices offered by middlemen who later increase retail prices in distant markets.

This pricing imbalance has been a recurring issue, creating tension between producers and resellers. Some producers have responded by joining cooperative groups such as the Women Cassava Processors Group, notably present in Ijebu-Igbo, Ago-Iwoye and Oru to negotiate better prices and share resources. Cooperative societies have also helped some women secure soft loans or participate in occasional agricultural support programmes from Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) or government agencies, although such initiatives remain sparse and inconsistent.^{xii} Efforts to preserve and extend the shelf life of *fufu* have further influenced marketing strategies. Fresh *fufu* typically lasts three days, while dried versions processed manually or under sun-drying methods can remain consumable for up to three months. This development has enabled some producers to store excess produce or engage in bulk sales to distant retailers.^{xiii} Despite this innovation, marketing remains largely manual or underdeveloped. Producers rarely use branding, labelling, or digital platforms. The lack of exposure to formal training, modern preservation methods (i.e., storing *fufu* in the refrigerator to keep it fresh for up to 3-5 days), and access to packaging technology continue to limit the scale at which *fufu* can be commercialised beyond local boundaries.

Nonetheless, the role of family labour remains central to marketing operations. Many *fufu* producers operate within family structures, where spouses and children assist with peeling, soaking, transporting, and selling. During peak periods such as harvest seasons or festive months, temporary labourers are hired to meet demand. This structure ensures that marketing activities are not only economic but also social, sustaining intergenerational knowledge and income flow within households.^{xiv} The marketing of *fufu* in Ijebu North is a dynamic but under-capitalised sector. It reflects how rural women navigate infrastructural, economic, and social constraints in the face of structural inequalities, market imbalances, and inadequate institutional support.

Fufu processing in Ijebu North Local Government is an age-old practice deeply entrenched in indigenous knowledge systems, gendered labour traditions, and rural

domestic economies. For decades, the art of turning cassava into consumable *fufu* has remained an intergenerational skill, transmitted through household observation, apprenticeship, and community practice. From early in the morning peeling late into the evening, sieving and drying, the process combines labour intensity with cultural discipline. The Ijebu women, primarily responsible for household food preparation, quickly adapted cassava for *fufu* production, complementing existing yam-based diets. The earliest processing involved rudimentary tools such as wooden mortars and stones used for pounding fermented tubers. Over time, these were replaced with locally fabricated graters, hand-pressed filter bags (known as *apoti*), and wood-fired stoves. The introduction of metal graters and mesh sieves signalled a semi-mechanised phase in the rural areas, and these innovations made the processing less strenuous, although most of the work still relied heavily on manual labour.^{xv}

3.3 Traditional processing of fufu

Respondents interviewed revealed that a largely consistent method occurred across the region, though with slight local variations. It is noted that the traditional *fufu* processing sequence involves stages, of which cassava peeling and washing is the first. Cassava peeling and washing is mostly done manually by women or hired helpers who use knives to peel the cassava. It is labourious and time-consuming, often requiring several hours per sack of cassava. Another stage is fermentation, and this occurs when the cassava is peeled and soaked in water, usually in large drums, basins, or earthen pits for 3 to 4 days, depending on weather conditions. The fermentation process is key to softening the tubers and giving *fufu* its characteristic taste. The next phase is mashing and sieving; the cassava is manually mashed using local graters. The paste is then sieved to remove fibers. This process, described as the most exhausting, is often shared among family members or communal groups.

Pressing is very important as it needs to be dried. The wet cassava mash is placed in porous sacks and manually pressed using stones or local wood presses to remove water. Some producers use lever-based manual presses fabricated by local welders. The next stage, however, is cooking or drying: For fresh *fufu*, the mash is cooked over fire into a moldable dough. For preservation, it is spread on trays or mats and sun-dried, taking advantage of the dry season for quick turnaround. This sequence takes an average of 5 to 7 days per batch, a timeline confirmed by multiple producers across Ago-Iwoye, Awa, and Ijebu-Igbo. The time variation depends on weather, cassava type, and access to water.^{xvi} The processing remains primarily manual. While local innovations such as hand-operated graters and makeshift presses still exist, there is minimal use of modern machines, such as flash dryers or automated graters. Most of the tools are self-funded and sourced from blacksmiths or local artisans. Attempts to mechanise the processing are confronted by obstacles such as inadequate electricity in most production areas, high cost of modern machines, limited training on the usage or maintenance. However, there is a growing awareness of modern methods. Some women indicated knowledge of flash dryers and hydraulic presses, though few have seen them physically. They expressed willingness to

adopt these technologies if supported with training and subsidies.^{xvii} This situation indicates that some of the women have been exposed and are willing to use these technologies in *fufu* business, but are financially constrained.

3.4 Fufu packaging and marketing in Ijebu-North local government area

Fufu packaging and marketing are essential for the continuous flow of the business. If farm products are not properly marketed, the entire production process is halted, thus negatively affecting the livelihood of the producers and every involved person. Packaging of agricultural commodities determines how fast the commodities would be purchased, since a good packaging system easily attracts customers. Proper packaging of *fufu* is very important after it has been produced because it prevents the product from being contaminated during transportation, thus extending the shelf life of the product.

There are major differences in packaging that exist between various forms of *fufu* (Dipeolu *et al*, 2001). The wet paste is normally packed in air-tight nylon and sealed in a coarser outer bag, a practice that is believed to help in preserving the wet paste. Ready-to-eat *fufu* balls are wrapped in *gbogogi* leaves or into polyethene sheets. Groups of about 40 wraps are then arranged in baskets, lined with cloth for sale to traders. Processors insist that the specific type of wrap used by them is the best one for extending the shelf life of the product; however, most traders and consumers do not seem to show a preference for any particular type of packaging (Dipeolu *et al*, 2001). This variant is more marketable beyond the local environment, lasting up to 3 months if properly dried and stored. Packaging remains informal and lacks standardised branding or labelling. While some cooperative groups have experimented with basic logos or stickers, most producers sell generically.

This reflects both a lack of regulatory enforcement and limited exposure to packaging standards required for urban and international markets. Mrs Janet explained that their customers purchased what they know; they don't really ask about expiry because of trust and the fact that they are familiar with them, which is a form of goodwill that enhances the selling of *fufu*.^{xviii} Storage is connected with packaging and performs a critical function in marketing systems since it allows for the period of availability of a certain product to be extended. Storage enables producers and traders to extend sales in order to take advantage of better prices. In addition, it tends to smooth variations in product availability due to seasonal or other factors, increasing the regularity of consumption throughout the year and reducing price instability. The convenience of a product to consumers is enhanced by the fact that storage permits larger purchases, thus reducing the number of trips to the market and transaction costs. When the product stays for a long time in the hands of the producers, it shortens the shelf life of the product with the marketing agents.

Therefore, it has to be passed to the consumers on time. (Dipeolu *et al*, 2001). Several precautions are taken by different market operators to minimise the extent of product deterioration during the time it is stored. For instance, while the wet paste is awaiting further processing or packaging into bags, it is often kept in plastic containers

covered with water, which is changed daily. Special care is taken to avoid product contamination with flies, dirt oil and other contaminants. Refrigeration is also widely adopted as a way of preserving the product, while ready-to-eat *fufu* balls are frequently kept in plastic warmers. In the case of the ready-to-eat product, however, thorough cooking appears to be the most effective and widespread precaution taken to prolong its shelf life. When properly cooked, ready-to-eat *fufu* may last for up to nine days (Ajala and Lasisi 2019).

Transportation is a critical activity in any agricultural commodity system, linking rural areas with more distant, often urban, markets. The degree of efficiency of transport systems is, therefore, a major determinant of market access, having a critical influence on producer and consumer prices. Given the normally long distances between scattered farms or points of processing and final destination markets, it is noted that transport costs generally account for a considerable share of total marketing costs. *Fufu* is transported by different means, including motorcycle (*Okada*), tricycle (*Keke-napep*), pick-up trucks and big trucks (Ajala and Lasisi 2019). Mr. Seyi reiterated that transportation of cassava from the farm to the place it will be processed and from the production point to the market affects the price of *fufu* in the market and likewise the size of the *fufu* packaged for sale.^{xix}

Environmental sanitation in *fufu* processing is usually an ongoing concern. Most producers lack access to clean processing environments, especially during the rainy season when waterlogged compounds and mud make cleanliness difficult. Despite this, it is noted that producers strive to maintain proper hygiene within the environment, even though wastewater from fermentation often flows into gutters, constituting offensive odour.^{xx} There have been sporadic health complaints, notably body pains, respiratory discomfort from fermentation odours, and skin irritations. However, due to the informal nature of the trade, there has been no systematised health inspection or documentation of long-term effects.^{xxi} Despite this, *fufu* producers have taken informal measures to ensure safety, such as sourcing clean water, discarding rotten tubers, and washing utensils with detergents.

3.5 Patronage and economic impact of *fufu* business

Fufu, as a staple food deeply rooted in the cultural and dietary preferences of the Yoruba people, continues to enjoy consistent demand in Ijebu North Local Government. Its patronage cuts across various social classes, age groups, and occupational groups, from daily wage earners and civil servants to students and traders. The availability of cassava and the affordability of *fufu* as a meal have been critical to its popularity among rural and peri-urban populations. Market days in towns like Ago-Iwoye, Ijebu-Igbo, Oru, and Awa are particularly lively with *fufu* trading. Market women sell both fresh and dried *fufu* weekly at the local market, and occasionally supply to traders travelling to urban centres like Lagos, Ibadan and Abeokuta. Similarly, some producers reserve large portions of their weekly produce for bulk buyers who resell in nearby towns and food joints.^{xxii}

The spread of *fufu* beyond Ijebu towns is also driven by returning students and travellers who purchased dried *fufu* to resell in urban centres. Traders from Lagos, Osogbo, and Benin are known to regularly patronise *fufu* hubs in Oru and Ago-Iwoye during the harvest season to purchase in bulk, recognising both the affordability and cultural preference for the Ijebu-style fermented taste. Patronage is notably higher during festive periods, such as Eid-el-Kabir, Christmas, and traditional festivals like Ojude Oba, when communal feasting and household demand increase. Producers often prepare larger quantities during such periods and may even employ temporary labour to meet demand.^{xxiii} The *fufu* trade in Ijebu North has historically been mediated by middlemen and market women, who serve as both transporters and resellers.

While these intermediaries facilitate the reach of *fufu* into broader markets, many producers express mixed feelings about their role. Mrs Abosede, in an interview, noted that the middlemen often dictated prices, paying less to producers while selling at inflated rates in the city. This sometimes reduces the profit margin for rural producers, particularly women who lack direct access to urban markets or transport options.^{xxiv} Despite these concerns, many processors rely on these intermediaries due to their market networks and bulk purchasing power. In response, several women's cooperatives have begun exploring direct-to-consumer models, including collaborations with food vendors, local eateries, and small grocery shops. This allows producers to bypass exploitative middlemen to earn better income while ensuring quality control.

The *fufu* business is not merely a subsistence activity; it plays a vital role in household sustenance, female empowerment, and local economic circulation. Almost all the women interviewed confirmed that *fufu* production has enabled them to pay their children's school fees, provide shelter, support their extended families, and purchase farming inputs for the next season. Mrs Bolanle, in an interview, stated that she made a weekly profit of ₦10,000 - ₦15,000 during peak seasons, and this has contributed to her being economically independent.^{xxv} Women involved in cassava farming and *fufu* processing often reinvest part of their profits into agricultural activities, buying improved cassava stems or hiring labour for land clearing. This creates a cyclical relationship between farming and processing that sustains household livelihoods. Even male family members often participated in the process, especially during harvesting or pressing, thus turning *fufu* production into a family-centred economic activity.^{xxvi} Beyond the household, *fufu* production provides employment opportunities for youths and casual labourers, particularly during cassava harvesting, peeling, and transport. Temporary workers, mostly women and teenage girls, are hired to support large orders or during festive seasons. However, critical limitations to youth engagement are the stigmatisation of manual labour and the lack of mechanised tools. Younger generations are more inclined to enter the business if equipped with modern equipment, such as processors and dryers, or if they receive grants from government programmes.

Despite its contributions, the *fufu* economy in Ijebu North is also plagued by price fluctuations, seasonal cassava scarcity, and infrastructural barriers. Farmers and processors lament the impact of the rising cost of cassava during the dry season, poor

road networks, which affect timely transport, lack of electricity, market levies and taxes imposed by local authorities. During lean periods, profit margins fall sharply, and some women resort to loans or small cooperative savings to stay afloat.^{xxvii} The financial pressures underscore the need for structural support through microcredit, equipment grants, and regulated pricing systems.

Fufu production in Ijebu North Local Government is a cornerstone of local agrarian commerce, connecting rural producers to larger urban food economies. What begins with the cultivation and harvesting of cassava in village farmlands eventually feeds a chain of activities, including processing, packaging, transportation, and retail. These processes involve multiple stakeholders, such as farmers, processors, *Okada* riders, tricycle drivers, traders, labourers, and market officials (Nwajiuba 1995). This interconnectivity has created a localised food economy that supports livelihoods beyond the immediate producers. For instance, the hiring of labourers for peeling and soaking, particularly during periods of bulk orders or festive seasons, ensures that a broader segment of the rural poor has access to short-term income opportunities. Similarly, the transport sector benefits as commercial riders ferry *fufu* from households to local markets and depots (Ajala and Lasisi, 2019, 167-176). Moreover, dried *fufu* transported to regional cities such as Abeokuta, Ibadan, and Lagos add to the inter-regional agricultural trade.

These movements are often informal but significant, as rural women capitalise on their extended family and trader networks to distribute *fufu* beyond Ijebu borders. This movement of goods contributes to rural-urban supply chains by sustaining food security and dietary for city-based Yoruba populations who prefer traditionally fermented Ijebu-style *fufu*. This economic flow demonstrates how what seems to be an informal local activity is actually embedded in a broader informal trade economy, which scholars have long identified as central to Nigeria's survivalist economic system, especially among women (Ibitunde *et al*, 2021, 32-38).

The *fufu* economy also contributes to local government revenue, especially through market levies, stall rentals, and produce taxes. In popular places such as Ago-Iwoye's Garage market, Ijebu-Igbo's Station market, and Obada market, *fufu* sellers pay regular fees to local councils or market associations. Though often seen as burdensome, these fees form part of the internally generated revenue (IGR) used for local administration. In some cases, market associations led by women (often called *Iyaloja*) play an important role in setting prices, resolving disputes, and enforcing hygiene. These groups act as both advocates for producers and enforcers of local trade customs. They also form rotating savings and credit schemes (*Ajo*), providing soft loans for women to expand their businesses or buy cassava during high-price seasons.^{xxviii}

The *fufu* economy in Ijebu North Local Government is overwhelmingly female-led, reflecting a gendered division of labour rooted in Yoruba culture. It is evident that women control every step of the production and marketing process, and *fufu* represents more than food; it is a symbol of economic agency, familial contribution, and social capital. *Fufu* production business gives not just income but status within families and communities. With earnings reinvested in children's education, home improvement, and

religious obligations, women's economic roles have been redefined through this enterprise. This has historical resonance, echoing the role of market women in precolonial and colonial Yoruba towns, where women organised commerce, financed religious festivals, and even influenced political decisions.^{xxix} While the labour is intensive, many women see *fufu* production as a path to independence, especially in cases where husbands are unemployed or irregularly employed. Furthermore, beyond its economic importance, *fufu* also serves as a strategic food security buffer because it can be stored (when dried) and consumed with a wide range of soups. *Fufu* provides a staple that can last through off-seasons, crises, or inflationary periods.

During the COVID-19 pandemic, for instance, many families in Ijebu North turned to locally produced *fufu*, as imported goods and packaged food became scarce or too expensive. It continues to serve as an affordable source of calories for both the poor and the middle class.^{xxx} Despite its vibrancy, the *fufu* economy faces serious sustainability challenges such as the absence of automated dryers or electric graters, thus prolonging the production time and increasing physical strain. Exposure to cassava fermentation fumes, repetitive physical labour, and standing for long hours lead to frequent body pains and respiratory discomfort among producers. Wastewater is often improperly disposed of or posed environmental risks due to its odour. Price fluctuations, driven by weather or market speculation, affect profit margins. Mr. Wasiu explained that during the dry season, cassava is usually scarce, and prices become double, forcing producers to reduce output.^{xxxi} It is therefore expedient for the government to provide occasional interventions through state agricultural programmes, such as small loans, training seminars, or cooperative support.

However, many producers remain unaware of or excluded from such schemes due to poor communication. Mrs Fadipe opined that the government need to set up a scheme to assist *fufu* producers.^{xxxii} The *fufu* production and marketing enterprise in Ijebu North Local Government represents a multi-layered economic, cultural, and gendered institution, deeply rooted in historical patterns of subsistence and market trade. It sustains households, employs hundreds, and fuels local food economies, yet it remains marginalised in policy discourse and infrastructural planning. A future-oriented strategy would require mechanised tools for small processors, access to credit, improved rural infrastructure, and targeted training in food safety and packaging.

4. CONCLUSION

Fufu production and marketing in Ijebu North Local Government is a testament to the resilience and creativity of rural dwellers who continue to sustain a traditional enterprise during modern economic challenges. The industry reflects a unique intersection of agriculture, gender roles, commerce, and cultural identity. This study maintained that *fufu* is not merely a food item, but a secured livelihood and social connector in Ijebu communities. The current system, though productive, is limited by infrastructural deficiencies, traditional constraints, and poor institutional support. In addition, without effective interventions, the sustainability of the *fufu* trade may be threatened, especially

with increasing rural-urban migration and climate-related impacts on cassava farming. The continuity of *fufu* production depends on empowering the local farmers, especially women, with tools, access to credit, training, and favourable market structures. More importantly, there is a need for policy attention to the value chain of local food processing. *Fufu* production provides a steady income, supports education and household welfare, generates rural employment, and contributes to local government revenue through market levies. *Fufu* production has ultimately contributed to food security in Ijebu-North Local Government Area.

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Internet Material

<https://burpy.com/how-to-reheat-fufu/>, assessed 30th May, 2025.

END NOTES

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- ⁱ Interview with Mrs. Aderonke Oyebola, 58 years old, Fufu processor, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ⁱⁱ Interview with Mrs. Fadipe Mary, 43 years old, Fufu processor, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, on 19/04/2025.
- ⁱⁱⁱ Interview with Mrs. Fadipe Mary, 43 years old, Fufu processor, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, on 19/04/2025.
- ^{iv} Interview with Mrs. Aderonke Oyebola, 58 years old, Fufu processor, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^v Interview with Mrs. Titi Adetola, 52 years old, Fufu processor, Awa-Ijebu, Ogun State, on 20/04/2025.
- ^{vi} Interview with Mrs. Ifashakin Bolanle, 55 years old, Fufu processor, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, on 20/04/2025.
- ^{vii} Interview with Mr. Seyi Adekola, 56 years old, Cassava farmer and supplier, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025/
- ^{viii} Interview with Mrs. Abosede Akinwumi, 63 years old, Fufu processor, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{ix} Interview with Mr. Seyi Adekola, 56 years old, Cassava farmer and supplier, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^x Interview with Mr. Basit Showande, 47 years old, Cassava farmer and supplier, Ago-Iwoye-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xi} Interview with Mrs. Fadipe Mary, 43 years old, Fufu producer, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, on 19/04/2025.
- ^{xii} Interview with Mrs. Titi Adetola, 52 years old, Fufu processor, Ijebu-Awa, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xiii} Interview with Mrs. Fadipe Mary, 43 years old, Fufu producer, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, on 19/04/2025.
- ^{xiv} <https://burpy.com/how-to-reheat-fufu/>, assessed 30th May, 2025.
- ^{xv} Interview with Mrs. Abosede Akinwumi, 63 years old, Fufu processor, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xvi} Interview with Mama. Janet Olowu, 74 years old, Fufu processor, Oru, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xvii} Interview with Miss. Blessing Odunayo, 24 years old, Fufu processor, Aiyetoro, Ogun State, on 20/04/2025.
- ^{xviii} Interview with Mama. Janet Olowu, 74 years old, Fufu processor, Oru, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xix} Interview with Mr. Seyi Adekola, 56 years old, Cassava farmer and supplier, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xx} Interview with Mrs. Fadipe Mary, 43 years old, Fufu producer, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, on 19/04/2025.
- ^{xxi} Interview with Mrs. Rofiat Oduntan, 53 years old, Fufu producer, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xxii} Interview with Mr. Kunle Ajiboye, 38 years old, Cassava farmer, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xxiii} Interview with Mr. Wasiu Ajibola, 58 years old, Cassava farmer and supplier, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xxiv} Interview with Mrs. Abosede Akinwumi, 63 years old, Fufu processor, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xxv} Interview with Mrs. Ifashakin Bolanle, 55 years old, Fufu processor, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, on 20/04/2025.
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- ^{xxix} Interview with Miss. Blessing Odunayo, 24 years old, Fufu processor, Aiyetoro, Ogun State, on 20/04/2025.
- ^{xxx} Interview with Mr. Wasiu Ajibola, 58 years old, Cassava farmer and supplier, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
- ^{xxxi} Interview with Mr. Wasiu Ajibola, 58 years old, Cassava farmer and supplier, Ijebu-Igbo, Ogun State, on 21/04/2025.
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